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5 **From hope to alert: demography of a remnant population of the Critically**
6 **Endangered *Atelopus varius* from Costa Rica**

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8 **José F. González-Maya^{1,2}, Diego A. Gómez-Hoyos^{1*}, Ivan Cruz-Lizano¹ & Jan Schipper^{1,3}**

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10 ¹ Proyecto de Conservación de Aguas y Tierras, ProCAT Colombia/Internacional-Fundación
11 Sierra to Sea Costa Rica, Las Alturas, Coto Brus, Puntarenas, Costa Rica. E-mail:

12 jfgonzalezmaya@gmail.com, dgomez@procat-conservation.org, icruz_009@yahoo.com

13 ² Instituto de Ecología, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Ciudad Universitaria,
14 México DF, México.

15 ³ Arizona Center for Nature Conservation–Phoenix Zoo, Phoenix, AZ, USA. E-mail:

16 globalmammal@gmail.com

17

18 *Corresponding Author: jfgonzalezmaya@gmail.com

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20 Abstract

21 Harlequin frogs have suffered severe declines across the Neotropics. We present a population
22 assessment for a recently discovered population of *Atelopus varius* from Costa Rica. Using
23 mark-recapture methods from September 2011 to February 2013, we estimated survival and

24 recruitments parameters using Cormack-Jolly-Seber models. We obtained 222 captures and
25 estimated low recruitment rates and high seniority. Given estimates of population growth rates
26 close to zero, the observed population seems to be stable during the study. However, contrary to
27 expectations for seasonally reproducing species like *A. varius*, we did not find an increase in
28 recruitment rates between dry and rainy season. We provide details on ongoing threats for the
29 population, as well as propose conservation actions to mitigate these threats.

30

31 Keywords: Amphibian decline; Capture-Recapture; Chytrid; Recruitment; Seniority; Trout.

32

33

34 Resumen

35 Las Ranas Arlequín han sufrido declives severos en el Neotrópico. Presentamos una evaluación
36 poblacional para una población recientemente descubierta de *Atelopus varius* de Costa Rica.

37 Usando métodos de marca-recaptura desde septiembre de 2011 hasta febrero de 2013, estimamos
38 parámetros de supervivencia y reclutamiento usando modelos Cormack-Jolly-Seber. Obtuvimos
39 222 capturas y estimamos bajas tasas de reclutamiento y alta “antigüedad” (*seniority*). Dadas que
40 las tasas de crecimiento poblacional se acercaron a cero, la población observada parece estar
41 estable durante el estudio. Sin embargo, contrario a lo esperado para especies con reproducción
42 estacional como *A. varius*, no encontramos un incremento en las tasas de reclutamiento entre las
43 estaciones lluviosa y seca. Proveemos detalles de amenazas actuales para la población, así como
44 propuestas de acciones de conservación para mitigar estas amenazas.

45

46 Palabras clave: declive de anfibios, captura-recaptura, Quitridio, reclutamiento, trucha.

47 **Introduction**

48 Frogs of the *Atelopus* genus, known as Harlequin Frogs, are distributed from Costa Rica down to
49 Bolivia and the Guianas in the South and East of their range, respectively (La Marca et al. 2005;
50 Lötters 1996; Lötters 2007). Except for some populations in Colombia, the Amazon and the
51 Guianas, Harlequin Frogs have suffered from rapid and severe population declines across their
52 entire distribution, leading to concerns regarding the potential extinction of the entire genus
53 (Lötters 2007). According to the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species (IUCN 2012), 74 of the
54 93 species are categorized as Critically Endangered, from which a large proportion is considered
55 potentially extinct (Lötters 2007).

56 Despite this dark prospects, some species that were thought to be extinct, or were
57 classified as data deficient, have been “rediscovered” and studied (Carvajalino-Fernández et al.
58 2008; Flechas et al. 2012; Gómez-Hoyos et al. 2014; Gómez-Hoyos et al. 2017; González-Maya
59 et al. 2013; Rueda-Solano 2012). These remnant populations offer a unique opportunity for the
60 study and development of conservation actions, providing hope for other *Atelopus* species
61 (Gómez-Hoyos et al. 2017; González-Maya et al. 2013; Perez et al. 2014).

62 Of the four harlequin frog species recorded in Costa Rica, only *Atelopus varius* has been
63 rediscovered from two localities during 2008 and 2015 (González-Maya et al. 2013, Barrio-
64 Amorós & Abarca 2016). For these surviving populations, management and conservation actions
65 seems warranted, since several factors considered to pose potential threats for amphibians - such
66 as pathogens, habitat degradation and invasive species - keep operating in these areas (JFG-M &
67 DAG-H, pers. obs.). Furthermore, post population decline surveys are critical for amphibian
68 conservation in general (Perez et al. 2014), because they help to identify threat factors driving
69 population declines, and help refine the management actions required. Here we estimated

70 population parameters for an *A. varius* population in Talamanca, Costa Rica and identified the
71 main threats for population persistence. Based on our results we specify urgent research needs
72 and propose management measures for *A. varius*.

73 **Materials and methods**

74 *Study area*

75 Our study site is located in the Las Tablas Protected Zone (LTPZ), Puntarenas Costa Rica. LTPZ
76 is located in Southeastern Costa Rica, specifically in the Talamanca mountain range, one of the
77 regions with higher levels of endemism of the country (González-Maya, Schipper, et al. 2013).
78 LTPZ spans for over 19000 ha, and it is part of La Amistad Biosphere Reserve (González-Maya
79 & Mata-Lorenzen 2008). Our study site is located in the Cotón river, at 1300 m asl, with a mean
80 annual precipitation of 3500 mm and mean annual temperature of 19° C that correspond to very
81 humid premontane tropical forest (González-Maya & Mata-Lorenzen 2008). In this site, the
82 landscape is dominated by mature and secondary forest, with some scarce patches of crops and
83 pastures.

84

85 *Survey*

86 Our surveys were conducted during the day on a 3 km transect along both sides of the Cotón
87 river. The transect was surveyed monthly from between September 2011 to February 2013, by a
88 herpetologist and a trained field assistant. The surveyors walked along the river margin covering
89 at least 2 m from the river bank, searching post-metamorph individuals as well as eggs and
90 tadpoles. Detected post-metamorph individuals were captured, measured (i.e., weight and snout-
91 to-vent length) and their dorsal and ventral surfaces were photographed. Samples from the skin
92 of each individual were obtained using cotton swabs for the study of *Batrachochytrium*

93 *dendrobatidis* (*Bd*) presence (Kriger et al. 2006), that were stored and refrigerated dry on sterile
94 vials for posterior testing. Data on location (i.e., geographic coordinates), time and substrate
95 were recorded for each individual, and a unique ID was assigned to each capture. Given that each
96 individual of *A. varius* exhibit a unique spotting pattern, capture histories were built based on
97 dorsal/ventral pictures of each captured individual. With the aim of avoiding transmission of *Bd*
98 between localities, we used exclusive wear and boots for our study area.

99

100 ***Data analysis***

101 We used the Cormack-Jolly-Seber (CJS) model based on live animal recaptures in an open
102 population (Lebreton et al. 1992) in order to estimate apparent survival. Apparent survival is the
103 probability that the animal remains alive and available for recapture and, technically, not the
104 survival probability of marked animals in the population (White & Burnham 1999). To confirm
105 that the CJS model adequately fitted the collected data, we used Bootstrap Goodness-of-fit test
106 (GOF). Analyses were conducted in program MARK 8.0 (White & Burnham 1999). Models
107 were constructed based on apparent survival (*Phi*) and recapture rates (*p*) with constant (.),
108 temporal (*t*: each monthly capture session) and seasonal variation (*season*: dry or rainy month
109 during the surveys) of such parameters, and for two age groups (immature individuals, including
110 juveniles and sub-adults: < 27 mm and mature individuals: > 27.1 mm). We used two seasons
111 (dry: December to March; rainy: April to November) as a temporal variation within models,
112 because Costa Rica has a marked bi-seasonal climatic pattern and *A. varius* is a seasonally-
113 reproductive species. A multi-state model was not considered because it assumes that all
114 individuals make the transitions at the same time, which is difficult to test for small sample sizes
115 such as in our study.

116 Seniority (*Gamma*) was estimated through Pradel ‘seniority only’ model. Since this
117 model computes encounter histories identical to the CJS model, we use the \hat{c} achieved by the
118 GOF test of the CJS model. Seniority probability (SP) is defined as the probability of an
119 individual to be alive and in the population at times i and $i-1$ (Pradel 1996). Thereby, SP is useful
120 for identifying the proportion of the population that was previously in the population before and
121 during reproductive season. In order to estimate the parameters involved in population growth,
122 we estimate recruitment and survival, and their interaction, as a base-line characteristic of the
123 population (Nichols et al. 2000). Also, the estimation of these parameter is useful to plan
124 conservation actions of threatened species (Schmidt et al. 2005; Muths et al. 2011). Pradel
125 survival and recruitment (PSR) model was used to estimate recruitment. Recruitment accounts
126 for the number of individuals added to a breeding population (Muths et al. 2011). In most
127 bufonid species, recruitment is not equal to reproduction given that individuals spend multiple
128 years as juveniles or immatures before joining the breeding population (Schmidt et al. 2005;
129 Muths et al. 2011); according to our field observations, in a seasonal breeding species such as *A.*
130 *varius*, new individuals entering the breeding population should come from cohorts near to
131 complete two years of development. Survival and recruitment parameters were used to calculate
132 *Atelopus varius* population growth (*Lambda*), or population size change rate, which has values
133 >1 indicating growth, and values <1 indicating decline (Muths et al. 2011).

134 The best-fitting models were selected based on the Akaike Information Criteria with a
135 correction for small sample sizes (AICc) and derived measures (Burnham & Anderson 1998;
136 Cooch & White 2015). When we found uncertainty about the best fitting model, we used a
137 model-averaging method with the top-ranked models (Delta AICc < 2), including only those

138 models with reliable estimations. All statistical results are presented with the respective Standard
139 Error (\pm SE) and 95% confidence intervals (LCI–UCI).

140

141 ***Threats assessment***

142 Swab samples were analyzed to confirm *Bd* presence in the population. Of 222 samples, we
143 selected 15 random sub-samples and these were tested for *Bd* using standardized methods (Hyatt
144 et al. 2007). We extracted DNA from the swabs with PrepMan Ultra (Applied Biosystems,
145 Carlsbad, California), and analyzed the samples using the standard real-time quantitative
146 polymerase chain reaction assay. We followed the standardized procedures in Boyle et al. (2004)
147 with the following exception: the nucleic acids were extracted using 50 μ l PrepMan, a negative
148 control (H₂O) and a positive control swab dipped in a broth of *Batrachochytrium dendrobatidis*
149 culture from Costa Rican strain JGA01. The presence of other potential threats such as habitat
150 perturbation and invasive species (e.g. rainbow trout) were registered (though not quantified)
151 during surveys in order to provide a first insight on possible influence of such pressures, since
152 these threats have been reported as potential drivers of decline in other populations (Pounds et al.
153 2010).

154

155 **Results**

156 We detected 222 individuals of *A. varius*, which included 103 immatures (23 juveniles and 80
157 sub-adults), as well as 113 male and female adults (6 undetermined; Figure 1). Uncertainty on
158 the identification between males and sub-adult females did not allow discrimination by sex
159 categories. Since it is expected that mature females present Snout Vent Length (SVL) usually

160 above 40 mm, our sample include at least 22 mature females. We did not detect any *A. varius*
161 eggs or tadpoles during our surveys, neither individuals under 18 mm SVL (Figure 1).

162 According to Bootstrap GOF the CJS model adequately fits the data ($\hat{c} = \sim 1$). Due to
163 uncertainty in selecting the best-fitting models, the model averaging method was applied to the 4
164 top-ranked models (Table 1); despite model 5 was also competent (Delta AICc = 1.912), the
165 estimate was not reliable. Considering model averaging, estimated apparent survival was
166 (estimate \pm standard error [95% confidence interval]) 0.87 ± 0.09 [0.59–0.97] in the rainy season
167 and 0.78 ± 0.16 [0.37–0.95] in the dry season. The capture probability varied over time from
168 0.011 ± 0.01 [0.002–0.069] to 0.1 ± 0.098 [0.013–0.48]. Regarding the estimation of SP, the two
169 best-fitting models explaining the data both included a capture probability depending on season,
170 and Gamma depending on season or constant, respectively (Table 1). Although the selection of
171 models including both a seasonal SP as well as a constant SP, and therefore the difference in SP
172 between seasons, was not substantially important, lower parameters were estimated from model
173 averaging for the dry season (0.5 ± 0.17 [0.20–0.79]) compared to rainy season (0.88 ± 0.07 [0.66–
174 0.97]). Capture probability was different between seasons; however, estimations were imprecise
175 (rainy: 0.01 ± 0.007 [0.005–0.04], dry: 0.095 ± 0.05 [0.03–0.26]). Meanwhile, the best-fitting
176 model including the estimation of recruitment comprised constant survival, constant recruitment,
177 as well as a capture probability varying over time (Table 1). Survival estimates for this model
178 (0.86 ± 0.07 [0.66–0.96]) were similar to the estimates with the CJS model, and recruitment was
179 estimated as 0.23 ± 0.07 [0.12–0.39]. Based on the estimates of recruitment and survival,
180 population size rate of change was 1.1 (0.78–1.35).

181 Tests for chytrid fungus were positive for two of the 15 individuals tested. Additionally,
182 during our surveys rainbow trout (i.e., invasive species) were detected repeatedly. Furthermore,

183 up to a distance of at least 500 m away from the survey area, the vegetation was under clearing
184 maintenance, indicating ongoing habitat transformation within the study area.

185

186 **Discussion**

187 Population parameters' estimates showed that the *A. varius* population from Las Tablas
188 Protected Zone was stable, with survival contributing more than recruitment as empirically
189 observed on both rates for our population; the estimation of these demographic components
190 allows to answer questions regarding population growth rates and explain the process that
191 represents the most important determinants for such phenomena (Nichols et al. 2000). This is
192 expected for long life expectancy species belonging to the *Atelopus* genus (Lötters 1996; Lampo
193 et al. 2012; Muths et al. 2011). *Atelopus varius* is considered a seasonal breeding species (Lötters
194 1996; Savage 2002), however, population parameters such as seniority and recruitment were
195 either not or weakly explained by seasonal reproduction, contrary to expected, possibly due to
196 the low capture rate. Although the population was stable during the survey, we argue that it can
197 be still considered vulnerable to local extinction given the low recruitment rates and high
198 seniority, and considering as base-line the elevated pre-decline population' estimates; the species
199 was considered locally abundant in the same area at least 20 years before our surveys (Pounds &
200 Crump 1994; La Marca et al. 2005; González-Maya et al. 2013).

201 Our apparent survival estimates were similar to those estimated for the species in El Copé
202 and Santa Marta in Panama prior to the arrival of *Bd* (McCaffery et al. 2015). They were also
203 similar to the survival parameter estimated for a population of *A. spumarius* from Ecuador that
204 tested negative for *Bd* (Tarvin et al. 2014). The similar survival estimates among these
205 populations, all under *Bd* pre-outbreak scenarios, indicate adult individuals are potentially not

206 severely affected by the infection, as shown in our population at least during our survey. Our
207 capture probabilities were similar to the lower limit estimates in these localities from Panama
208 (McCaffery et al. 2015), but were substantially lower than those estimated for *A. spurrelli* and *A.*
209 *elegans* in Colombia (Gómez-Hoyos et al. 2014; Gómez-Hoyos et al. 2017), which likely
210 contributed to the considerably large confidence intervals of parameter estimates in our study.

211 No data is available concerning survivorship of froglets, tadpoles or eggs of the species in
212 our study or elsewhere (Lötters 1996), and we did not detected any tadpoles or eggs during our
213 surveys. We found no evidence for seasonal differences in recruitment, and only weak influence
214 of season on seniority (Table 1), contrary to what would be expected for species with marked
215 seasonal reproduction (during dry season) (Lötters 1996; Savage 2002). Although the absence of
216 individuals below 18 mm SVL could be explained by their very low capture probability.

217 We found that threats to the population are still operating in the area, as was previously
218 detected by Lips et al. (2003). Habitat loss have not ceased since the reported disappearing of the
219 population in the area. During the last half of the twentieth century our study area was subject to
220 logging and forest cover change due to the expansion of coffee production and pastures for
221 cattle. Even though in the first decade of the 21st century logging was stopped in the area, and
222 coffee plantations and cattle raising were considerably reduced, the area inhabited by *A. varius* is
223 still subject to a low degree of cattle grazing. Chytrid fungus was detected and still potentially
224 threatens the survival of this population. Although these results are based on a small sample size,
225 and should be regarded only as confirmation of presence of the fungus in the population, we
226 consider this information relevant for our study; not only this is the first record to *Bd* presence in
227 *A. varius* population from LTPZ, but also it is likely the most important threat based on the

228 severe consequences detected in populations of other species upon the arrival of *Bd* (Ryan et al.
229 2008; Crawford et al. 2010).

230 Previous studies have suggested habitat degradation as one of the main causes of
231 *Atelopus* decline throughout its range (La Marca et al. 2005); for instance, survival of *A.*
232 *spumarius* decreased after selective tree harvest within its habitat (Tarvin et al. 2014). Also,
233 rainbow trout has shown constant presence in recent years; the species was introduced to Costa
234 Rica as early as 1927-1928, but it was extensively cultured only since 1988, mainly on the higher
235 parts of Talamanca and other mountain ranges (Vargas 2003). During our field surveys we
236 frequently detected the presence of the species both in the main river and isolated ponds and
237 tributaries. We hypothesized that rainbow trout might cause population decline by preying on
238 eggs, and probably to a minor extent on tadpoles and metamorphs. *Atelopus varius* lay egg
239 strings on streams and rivers (Lötters 1996) and are probably very susceptible to predation by
240 trout (La Marca et al. 2005; Martín-Torrijos et al. 2016) and other aquatic predators.

241 We do acknowledge that our results did not test causality or positive/negative
242 relationships between potential threats and population parameters. However, we believe these
243 causes have plausible probability to be affecting the survival of the population. Especially since
244 they were already positively related with *Atelopus* decline both globally and in Costa Rica
245 (Berger et al. 1998; Blaustein et al. 1994; La Marca et al. 2005).

246 In order to avoid the local extinction of this population, we propose three main
247 conservation/management actions: 1) entrance of other strains of *Bd* must be avoided by
248 establishing a biosafety protocol, including disinfection of potential carriers of zoospores (e.g.,
249 tires, equipment, boots, etc.) for accessing the river; 2) enclosures around located breeding sites
250 to reduce predation on eggs or tadpoles; 3) habitat loss and degradation must be stopped (e.g.,

251 maintenance of legal protection areas in the river banks) to maintain suitable conditions around
252 the core population. All proposed measures will need to be assessed through permanent
253 population monitoring in order to test its effectiveness on reducing the risk for this population.

254 Finally, the good and encouraging news of the rediscovery of this “Lazarus” population
255 also brought serious challenges to ensure its survival in spite of the continuing threats. The
256 stable/positive growth rate of the population estimated in our study is promising, although this
257 result has to be interpreted with great caution due to the low capture rates in this study. However,
258 these low capture rates are at the same time an indication that abundance is considerably lower
259 than estimated before (La Marca et al. 2005; Pounds & Crump 1994), which calls for the
260 incorporation of the suggested measures plus continuing close monitoring and research of the
261 population in order to obtain more clues on how to secure these unique populations in the long
262 term.

263

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269

270 *Literature cited*

271

272

273 Barrio-Amorós CL, Abarca J. 2016. Another surviving population of the Critically Endangered

274 *Atelopus varius* (Anura: Bufonidae) in Costa Rica. *Mesoamerican Herpetology* 3:1-7.

275 Berger L, Spearea R, Daszak P, Greene DE, Cunningham AA, Goggin CL, Slocombe R, Ragan
276 MA, Hyatt AD, McDonald KR and others. 1998. Chytridiomycosis causes amphibian
277 mortality associated with population declines in the rain forests of Australia and Central
278 America. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 95:9031-9036.

279 Blaustein AR, Wake DB, Sousa WP. 1994. Amphibian Declines: Judging Stability, Persistence,
280 and Susceptibility of Populations to Local and Global Extinctions. *Conservation Biology*
281 8:60-71.

282 Boyle DG, Boyle DB, Olsen V, Morgan JA, Hyatt AD. 2004. Rapid quantitative detection of
283 chytridiomycosis (*Batrachochytrium dendrobatidis*) in amphibian samples using real-time
284 Taqman PCR assay. *Dis Aquat Organ* 60:141-8.

285 Burnham KP, Anderson DR. 1998. *Model Selection and Multimodel Inference: A Practical*
286 *Information-Theoretic Approach*. New York, US: Springer-Verlag.

287 Carvajalino-Fernández JM, Cuadrado-Peña B, Ramírez-Pinilla MP. 2008. Registros adicionales
288 de *Atelopus nahumae* y *Atelopus laetissimus* para la Sierra Nevada de Santa Marta,
289 Colombia. *Actualidades Biológicas* 30:97-103.

290 Cooch E, White GC. 2015. *Program Mark: a gentle introduction*. Ithaca, New York, USA.

291 Crawford AJ, Lips KR, Bermingham E. 2010. Epidemic disease decimates amphibian
292 abundance, species diversity, and evolutionary history in the highlands of central Panama.
293 *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 107: 13777-13782.

294 Flechas SV, Sarmiento C, Amezquita A. 2012. Bd on the beach: high prevalence of
295 *Batrachochytrium dendrobatidis* in the lowland forests of Gorgona Island (Colombia,
296 South America). *Ecohealth* 9:298-302.

297 Gómez-Hoyos DA, Bolívar-G. W, Burbano-Yandi CE, García JL. 2014. Evaluación poblacional
298 y estrategia de monitoreo para *Atelopus spurrelli* en el Parque Nacional Natural Utría,
299 Colombia. *Revista Biodiversidad Neotropical* 4:104-112.

300 Gómez-Hoyos DA, Suárez-Joaqui T, Bolívar W, García JL. 2017. Population Assessment
301 Strategy for *Atelopus elegans* (Bufonidae) in the Gorgona National Natural Park,
302 Colombia. *North-Western Journal of Zoology* 13:154–158.

303 González-Maya JF, Belant JL, Wyatt SA, Schipper J, Cardenal-Porras J, Corrales D, Cruz-
304 Lizano I, Hoepker A, Escobedo-Galván AH, Castañeda FE and others. 2013. Renewing
305 hope: the rediscovery of *Atelopus varius* in Costa Rica. *Amphibia-Reptilia* 34:573-578.

306 González-Maya JF, Mata-Lorenzen J. 2008. Dung-beetles (Coleoptera: Scarabeidae) from the
307 Zona Protectora Las Tablas, Costa Rica. *Checklist* 4:458–463.

308 González-Maya JF, Schipper J, Hoepker A. 2013. Talamanca montane forests. In: Howarth R,
309 editor. *Biomes and ecosystems: an encyclopedia*. Ipswich, MA, USA: Salem Press. p 1203-
310 1205.

311 Hyatt AD, Boyle DG, Olsen V, Boyle DB, Berger L, Obendorf D, Dalton A, Kriger K, Hero M,
312 Hines H and others. 2007. Diagnostic assays and sampling protocols for the detection of
313 *Batrachochytrium dendrobatidis*. *Diseases of Aquatic Organisms* 73:175-192.

314 IUCN. 2012. IUCN Red List of Threatened Species. IUCN Red List of Threatened Species
315 Version 2012.2. Gland, Switzerland: International Union for Conservation of Nature.

316 Kriger KM, Hines HB, Hyatt AD, Boyle DG, Hero JM. 2006. Techniques for detecting
317 chytridiomycosis in wild frogs: comparing histology with real-time Taqman PCR. *Dis*
318 *Aquat Organ* 71:141-8.

319 La Marca E, Lips KR, Lötters S, Puschendorf R, Ibáñez R, Rueda-Almonacid JV, Schulte R,
320 Marty C, Castro F, Manzanilla-Puppo J and others. 2005. Catastrophic population declines
321 and extinctions in neotropical harlequin frogs (Bufonidae: *Atelopus*). *Biotropica* 37:190-
322 201.

323 Lampo M, Celsa SJ, Rodríguez-Contreras A, Rojas-Runjaic F, García CZ. 2012. High turnover
324 rates in remnant populations of the harlequin frog *Atelopus cruciger* (Bufonidae): Low risk
325 of extinction? *Biotropica* 44:420-426.

326 Lebreton J-D, Burnham KP, Clobert J, Anderson DR. 1992. Modeling survival and testing
327 biological hypotheses using marked animals: a unified approach with case studies.
328 *Ecological Monographs* 62:67-118.

329 Lips KR, Green E, Papendick R. 2003. Chytridiomycosis in wild frogs from southern Costa
330 Rica. *J Herpetol* 37:215-218.

331 Lötters S. 1996. The Neotropical Toad Genus *Atelopus*. Checklist - Biology - Distribution.
332 Vences M, Glaw F, editors. Koln, Germany: Verlags GbR.

333 Lötters S. 2007. The fate of the harlequin toads – help through a synchronous multi-disciplinary
334 approach and the IUCN ‘Amphibian Conservation Action Plan’? *Mitteilungen aus dem*
335 *Museum für Naturkunde in Berlin – Zoologische Reihe* 83:69-73.

336 Martín-Torrijos L, Sandoval-Sierra JV, Muñoz J, Diéguez-Uribeondo J, Bosch J, Guayasamin
337 JM. 2016. Rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) threaten Andean amphibians. *Neotropical*
338 *Biodiversity* 2:26-36.

339 McCaffery R, Richards-Zawacki CL, Lips KR. 2015. The demography of *Atelopus* decline:
340 Harlequin frog survival and abundance in central Panama prior to and during a disease
341 outbreak. *Global Ecology and Conservation* 4:232-242.

342 Muths E, Scherer RD, Pilliod DS. 2011. Compensatory effects of recruitment and survival when
343 amphibian populations are perturbed by disease. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 48:873-879.

344 Perez R, Richards-Zawacki CL, Krohn AR, Robak M, Grigfith EJ, Ross H, Gratwicke B, Ibañez
345 R, Voyles J. 2014. Field surveys in Western Panama indicate populations of *Atelopus*
346 *varius* frogs are persisting in regions where *Batrachochytrium dendrobatidis* is now
347 enzootic. *Amphibian & Reptile Conservation* 8:30-35.

348 Pounds, J., Puschendorf, R., Bolaños, F., Chaves, G., Crump, M., Solís, F., Ibañez, R., Savage,
349 J., Jaramillo, C., Fuenmayor, Q. & Lips, K. 2010. *Atelopus varius*. The IUCN Red List of
350 Threatened Species 2010: e.T54560A11167883. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2010->
351 [2.RLTS.T54560A11167883.en](http://dx.doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2010-2.RLTS.T54560A11167883.en).

352 Pounds JA, Crump ML. 1994. Amphibian declines and climate disturbance: the case of the
353 golden toad and the harlequin frog. *Conservation Biology* 8:72-85

354 Pradel R. 1996. Utilization of capture-mark-recapture for the study of recruitment and population
355 growth rate. *Biometrics* 52:703-709.

356 Rueda-Solano LA. 2012. *Atelopus carrikeri* Ruthven, 1916 (Anura: Bufonidae) una especie
357 policromática. *Herpetotropicos* 8:61-66.

358 Ryan MJ, Lips KR, Eichholz MW. 2008. Decline and extirpation of an endangered Panamanian
359 stream frog population (*Craugastor punctariolus*) due to an outbreak of chytridiomycosis.
360 *Biological Conservation* 141: 1636-1647.

361 Schmidt BR, Feldmann R, Schaub M. 2005. Demographic processes underlying population
362 growth and decline in *Salamandra salamandra*. *Conservation Biology* 19:1149-11*56.

- 363 Tarvin RD, Peña P, Ron SR. 2014. Changes in population size and survival in *Atelopus*
364 *spumarius* (Anura: Bufonidae) are not correlated with chytrid prevalence. Journal of
365 Herpetology 48:291-297.
- 366 Vargas R. 2003. Evaluación de la reproducción de trucha arcoiris (*Onchorhynchus mykiss*)
367 producida en Costa Rica. I Parte. Agronomía Mesoamericana 14:123-127.
- 368 White GC, Burnham KP. 1999. Program MARK: survival estimation from populations of
369 marked animals. Bird study 46:120-138.

370 **Table 1.** Top-ranked models for *Atelopus varius* apparent survival, recruitment and seniority
 371 probability from Las Tablas Protected Zone, Costa Rica. Model averaging was performed to
 372 models with Delta AICc < 2.

Model	AICc	Delta AICc	AICc Weights	Model Likelihood	k	Deviance
<i>Apparent survival</i>						
<i>Phi(.)p(season)</i>	178.470	0.000	0.234	1.000	3	84.275
<i>Phi(.) p(t)</i>	179.535	1.065	0.137	0.587	16	56.652
<i>Phi(season)p(t)</i>	179.828	1.358	0.118	0.507	17	54.578
<i>Phi(season)p(season)</i>	179.961	1.491	0.111	0.474	4	83.688
<i>Phi(age)p(season)</i>	180.382	1.912	0.089	0.384	4	84.109
<i>Phi(.)p(.)</i>	181.660	3.190	0.047	0.203	2	89.524
<i>Phi(age)p(t)</i>	181.867	3.397	0.043	0.183	17	56.617
<i>Phi(.)p(season*age)</i>	182.206	3.736	0.036	0.154	5	83.834
<i>Phi(.) p(g)</i>	183.093	4.623	0.023	0.099	3	88.898
<i>Pradel seniority</i>						
<i>Gamma(season)p(season)</i>	179.635	0.000	0.522	1	4	-935.597
<i>Gamma(.)p(season)</i>	180.215	0.579	0.390	0.748	3	-932.943
<i>Gamma(.)p(.)</i>	184.400	4.765	0.048	0.092	2	-926.702
<i>Gamma(season)p(.)</i>	186.346	6.711	0.018	0.035	3	-926.811
<i>Gamma(.)p(t)</i>	186.815	7.180	0.014	0.028	16	-954.898
<i>Gamma(season)p(t)</i>	188.292	8.657	0.007	0.013	17	-955.770
<i>Gamma(t)p(season)</i>	198.058	18.422	0.000	0.0001	17	-946.004
<i>Gamma(t)p(.)</i>	200.449	20.814	0.000	0.000	16	-941.264
<i>Gamma(t)p(t)</i>	203.244	23.609	0.000	0.000	27	-965.637
<i>Pradel recruitment</i>						
<i>Phi(.)p(t)f(.)</i>	1209.240	0.000	0.502	1	18	62.807
<i>Phi(.) p(t)f(season)</i>	1211.265	2.025	0.183	0.363	19	62.437
<i>Phi(season)p(t)f(.)</i>	1211.442	2.201	0.167	0.333	19	62.614
<i>Phi(.)p(t)f(t)</i>	1211.689	2.449	0.148	0.294	22	55.532
<i>Phi(.)p(season)f(t)</i>	1228.038	18.797	0.000	0.000	12	95.491
<i>Phi(t)p(t)f(t)</i>	1230.875	21.635	0.000	0.000	33	45.828
<i>Phi(.)p(.)f(t)</i>	1235.956	26.716	0.000	0.000	12	103.409
<i>Phi(season)p(.)f(t)</i>	1238.051	28.811	0.000	0.000	13	103.246
<i>Phi(t) p(.)f(t)</i>	1238.551	29.311	0.000	0.000	26	72.267

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374 **Figure 1.** Distribution of age proportions of *Atelopus varius* individuals from Las Tablas
 375 Protected Zone, Costa Rica. (a) metamorphs: 7 mm, (b) juveniles: <21.5 mm, (c) subadults:
 376 21.5–27 mm and (d) adults: 27–43 mm (adult females: 33–43 mm).

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